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CANDIDATE EXPERIENCE OF AI IN TALENT ACQUISITION: A STUDY ON THE IT SECTOR**DR. SWETA BANERJEE AND DR. MITTAL MOHITE****ABSTRACT**

With the advent of technology and its varied uses in the business world, there are drastic changes in the way the organizations of today are functioning. Artificial Intelligence is one of many trending technologies and can almost be considered as ubiquitous in today's time. Artificial Intelligence (AI) as the name suggests is the replication of human intelligence into machines that are organized to think and function like humans. Businesses are slowly yet steadily moving towards AI because of its capability to rationalize and take business decisions that have the best chance of achieving the set goals, without direct human intervention. Candidate experience would essentially be the perception and experience a job seeker undergoes with the organisation and the employer while undertaking the Talent Acquisition process. It refers to the experience the candidate has with the employer during the course of the recruitment process. This experience is important in order to determine the image of the organisation. Thus, this research paper aims to evaluate the impact of AI on the talent acquisition process specifically on candidate experience. This study also tries to understand if the candidate experience is likely to cause some kind of positive employer brand in the market.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Candidate Experience; Employer branding; AI-recruitment

INTRODUCTION

Candidate experience and employer branding are quite prominent. AI technologies are enabling the organisations to increase their reach and attract great talent from a wider geographic area. Along with this, the role of importance of HR as a business function is moving beyond just, screening, sourcing and calling candidates for interviews. As stated by, (Dijkkamp, 2019), AI transforms the role of HR professionals from a sourcing and screening role to a relationship building and stakeholder management role in which the HR professionals enable a positive candidate experience for new employees.

Candidate experience in general would refer to the feelings and experiences of candidates or potential employees during their interaction with the employer/organisation that is conducting the hiring process. It refers to the candidate's perception about company's recruiting and hiring process (talentlyft, n.d.) In another paper authored by (McCamey, 2018) it was highlighted that candidate experience refers to the exchange between job seekers or candidates and the organisation to which the employment is being considered. The exchange would be through the activities undertaken by both parties. Candidates engage in activities that allows them to encounter opportunities with the organisations and organisations engage in activities that allow them to fill a job position. Thus, we can say that candidate experience is gaining immense importance in today's business world. For better understanding, we can draw a parallel between the external customer of the organisation and its internal customers, i.e., its employees/potential employees. A document published by (Retorio) creates a comparison between how customers of today's time and date, want a fast, effective, personalised processes at the click of mouse. Similarly, applicants of today, want a rapid, effective, trusted and personalised interview process. As mentioned in the paper, "AI-recruitment is the Amazon of candidate experience" and subsequent employer branding which offers a rapid, effective and highly personalised hiring process to job seekers. There are mainly 5 touch-points in the recruitment process that needs to be taken care of to ensure good candidate experience, i.e., Initial Job search, application process, job interviews, feedback-offer-rejection, onboarding. The paper argues that the organisations that fail to optimise their candidate experience will eventually lose top talent and good candidates and also create a negative employer brand. Having a bad candidate experience will eventually lead to either of the following

1. Scaring away eligible candidates,
2. Creating a bad employer brand
3. Losing potential customers that are candidates.

AI-technologies can have a deep impact on understanding these talent acquisition touch-points.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The field of Human Resources has been evolving in terms of the methods, policies and practices required to function, over the years. In today's time, the HR domain is still experiencing crucial changes that will change the shape and nature of how HR functions in any organisation. As mentioned by (Patrick van Esch, 2019) the role of HR has moved from being Tactical in nature to Strategic in nature. It states that recruitment too is a strategic business priority and cannot be just tactical in nature. This drastic change is mainly because the focus of competitive advantage for firms has shifted from tangible assets to intangible assets such as innovation, customer insight, customer service and brand and this shift has increased the emphasis on human capital. Thus, when the role of HR is becoming more and more strategic, AI-enabled recruiting is becoming a critical capability that organisations will have to adapt in order to attract, develop and retain a workforce that is slowly and gradually moving onto digital spaces and interacting extensively with technology.

According to, (Nishad Nawaz, 2019) the new cognitive technologies such as AI-driven Chatbots have gained immense popularity when it comes to recruitment and the overall talent acquisition process. These technologies have smart ways of collecting data of the candidate and thus, improve recruitment effectiveness. Among the many benefits of using AI-Chatbots, as stated by (Nishad Nawaz, 2019), this allows us to conduct an analysis of whether such technologies, enhance or weaken the Candidate experience and subsequent employer branding for any organisation.

Employer Branding as defined in (Kumar, 2017) as an attempt of the organisation and employer to establish a unique identity so as to attract and retain employees. This paper also highlights that the implementation of AI in the organisation allows the organisation to streamline its operations and also manage its human capital better. Earlier, employer branding was catered to using the various tabs on website, or professional social networking sites. Now Digital employer branding is taking over with the help of new technologies and AI that help organisations carry out activities such as preparing professional recruitment videos, running company blogs, interactive games, publishing newsletters, managing chats, and participating in online (virtual) job fairs. It is believed that, the candidates that have a smooth experience with the organisation look forward to more interactions with the employer company through various modes such as purchasing their products, referring the brand to their friends and families, giving good online reviews, thus, positively impacting the employer branding. It can also be said that the HR department and its activities can be continually shaped and refined with the AI solutions to make the organisations the desired employers in the labour market. "Automation of processes such as recruitment and selection, onboarding, improvement, and talent management significantly facilitates work, including increasing objectivity in action, introducing important standards. Such solutions as ATS, TAS, LMS and chatbots revolutionize the business while allowing to shape the image of an organization as a modern employer" (Kumar, 2017)

It can be observed that most of the available literature are mainly qualitative studies based on secondary sources of information and cover aspects depicting the pros and cons of using AI-technologies on candidate experience and subsequently on employer branding. However, there is a scarcity of empirical research that allows us to gauge the actual impact of implementing AI on the candidate's overall experience and further on employer branding. This is the research gap identified in this paper and thus, the research problem that we will be addressing in through this paper would be to **Critically analyse the effect and impact of AI in the talent acquisition process, specifically on candidate experience.**

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

1. To investigate the impact of AI on candidate experience in talent acquisition process.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVE

1. To assess whether candidate experience varies with the gender of the candidate.
2. To assess if candidate experience varies with the grade levels of position for which the hiring is being done.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no impact of AI on candidate experience during the Talent acquisition process

H₀: Candidate experience does not vary with the gender of the candidate.

H₀: Candidate experience does not vary with the grade levels of the position for which the hiring is being done

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an empirical study conducted with the help of primary data collected from job seekers in the IT sector. The data is collected from 60 respondents and is analysed using IBM SPSS 26.00.

It is a quantitative research conducted to study the impact of AI on candidate experience when implemented in the talent acquisition process.

DATA ANALYSIS

1. Reliability test

Scale: Artificial Intelligence

Table 1: AI case summary

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	60	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	60	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 1.1 Reliability analysis of AI

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.828	5

Scale: Candidate Experience

Table 2. Case summary for Candidate Exp.

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	60	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	60	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 2.1. Reliability analysis of Candidate Exp.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.855	13

Since the Cronbach Alpha score of the independent variable, i.e., Artificial Intelligence and Dependent Variable, i.e., Candidate experience is 0.828 and 0.855 respectively, which is greater than .7 we can conclude that the data is reliable.

2. NORMALITY TEST

2.1 Artificial Intelligence

Table 3. Skewness and Kurtosis values for AI

Descriptives			Statistic	Std. Error
Artificial intelligence	Mean		26.95	.616
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	25.72	
		Upper Bound	28.18	
	5% Trimmed Mean		27.09	
	Median		28.00	
	Variance		22.760	
	Std. Deviation		4.771	
	Minimum		10	
	Maximum		35	
	Range		25	
	Interquartile Range		7	
	Skewness		-.823	.309
	Kurtosis		1.258	.608

From the above table 3 we can observe that the absolute skewness and kurtosis values for the first variable, i.e., Artificial Intelligence are 0.823 and 1.258 respectively. These values are less than 3, hence we can conclude by saying that the variable data is normally distributed.

Fig. 1: Q-Q Plot for AI

The below box plot fig. 2 shows that the Artificial intelligence variable has an outlier (respondent 14). This is the extreme value in data gathered.

Fig. 2. Box Plot for AI

1.2 Candidate Experience

Table 4. Skewness and Kurtosis values for Candidate Experience

Descriptives				
		Statistic	Std. Error	
Candidate experience	Mean	70.27	1.252	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	67.76	
		Upper Bound	72.77	
	5% Trimmed Mean	70.30		
	Median	72.00		
	Variance	94.097		
	Std. Deviation	9.700		
	Minimum	45		
	Maximum	91		
	Range	46		
	Interquartile Range	13		
	Skewness	-.228	.309	
	Kurtosis	.101	.608	

From the above table 4 we can observe that the absolute skewness and kurtosis values for the first variable, i.e., Candidate Experience are -0.228 and 0.101 respectively. These values are less than 3, hence we can conclude by saying that the variable data is normally distributed.

Fig. 3. Q-Q Plot for Candidate exp.

The below box plot fig. 4 shows that the Candidate experience variable does not have outliers and hence we have clean box plot for the dependent variable.

Fig. 4: Box plot for candidate experience

3. STATISTICS

2.1. Descriptive statistics:

3.1.1. Frequencies

Table 5: Descriptive statistics for AI, Candidate exp., Employer branding

		Statistics		
		Artificial intelligence	Candidate experience	Employer branding
N	Valid	60	60	60
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		26.95	70.27	3.75
Median		28.00	72.00	4.00
Mode		30	75	4
Std. Deviation		4.771	9.700	1.002
Variance		22.760	94.097	1.004
Skewness		-.823	-.228	-.830

Std. Error of Skewness	.309	.309	.309
Kurtosis	1.258	.101	.505
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.608	.608	.608
Minimum	10	45	1
Maximum	35	91	5

2.1.2. Gender statistics:

Table 6: Gender statistics

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	34	56.7	56.7	56.7
	2	26	43.3	43.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Fig 5: Pie-chart showing gender of respondents

For the purpose of this study, Male respondents were coded as 1 and Female respondents were coded as 2. Out of the total number of respondents, 56.7% of the respondents i.e., 34 respondents were male and 43.3% respondents i.e., 26 respondents were female.

2.1.3. Age Statistics:

Table 7: Age statistics

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	33	55.0	55.0	55.0
	2	18	30.0	30.0	85.0
	3	9	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

For the purpose of this study, 3 age groups were considered. The first age group was 18-24 years of age which are the Gen Z. They are coded as 1 in the above table. The second age group was 25-40 years which are considered as Millennials and coded as 2 for this study. Lastly, the age of group between 41- 56 years, categorised as Gen X and coded as 3 for the purpose of this study.

In this study, we observe that 55% of the respondents belonged to the Gen Z in the age group of 18-24 years and 30% belonged to the age group of 25-40 years. The remaining 15% belonged to Gen X.

Fig. 6: Pie-chart showing age of respondents

2.1.4. Management Level

Table 8: Grade level statistics

Management level					
		Frequency	Percent	ValidPercent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	38	63.3	63.3	63.3
	2	8	13.3	13.3	76.7
	3	5	8.3	8.3	85.0
	4	9	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Fig. 7: Bar chart showing grade level of respondents

For the purpose of this study, I tried to understand which level of management does the candidate interview for in order to further understand whether the experience would vary with change in management levels. The management levels I undertook is as follows:

Management level	Code for this study
Entry level (approx. 0-2 years of experience)	1
Executive/Associate level (3-6 years of experience)	2
Middle-level (7-10 years of experience)	3
Top-level (>11 years of years)	4

63.3% of the respondents interviewed for entry-level positions. Followed by 15% belonging to top-level management roles.

Moving onto to inferential statistics in order to test the hypothesis and study the objectives mentioned previously.

3.2. Inferential Statistics:

3.2.1. Correlation:

Table 9: Correlation between variables

Correlations			
		Artificial intelligence	Candidate experience
Artificial intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	.572 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1342.850	1561.800
	Covariance	22.760	26.471
	N	60	60
Candidate experience	Pearson Correlation	.572 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1561.800	5551.733
	Covariance	26.471	94.097
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As we can see, the Pearson’s Correlation score between the dependent and independent variable is 0.572 and therefore we can conclude that there is a **moderate positive correlation** between AI and candidate experience.

Secondly, since the significance value i.e., $p= 0.000$, is less than 0.5. Hence, we can conclude that there is a significant association between the variables.

3.2.2. Regression:

Table 10: Model summary of regression

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.572 ^a	.327	.316	8.025
a. Predictors: (Constant), Artificial intelligence				
b. Dependent Variable: Candidate experience				

The value of R Square denotes the model fit. The R square value in percentages would be 32.7% . This denotes that 32.7% of the variance caused in the dependent variable (candidate exp.) is because of the independent variable (AI).

Table 11: ANOVA Table of regression

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1816.450	1	1816.450	28.205	.000 ^b
	Residual	3735.284	58	64.401		
	Total	5551.733	59			
a. Dependent Variable: Candidate experience						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Artificial intelligence						

In the ANOVA Table 11., we observe that significance value, $p= 0.000$, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that there is a significant relation between the two variables.

Table 12: Unstandardized Coefficient table

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	38.923	5.992		6.496	.000	26.928	50.917
Artificial intelligence	1.163	.219	.572	5.311	.000	.725	1.601

a. Dependent Variable: Candidate experience

As per the Coefficients table, the unstandardized coefficients we get the equation; Candidate experience= 38.923+ (1.163) (Artificial Intelligence)

3.3. Hypothesis Testing for Secondary objectives

3.3.1. Ho: Candidate experience does not vary with the gender of the candidate.

T-Test

Group Statistics					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Candidate experience	1	34	69.18	9.427	1.617
	2	26	71.69	10.051	1.971

On observing the group statistics, Female respondents (coded as 2) have a higher mean for candidate experience when compared to Male respondents (coded as 1). This highlights that female respondents are more likely to have a better candidate experience due to AI as compared to the Male respondents.

Table 13: Independent T-test for candidate exp. and gender

Independent Sample Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper	
Candidate experience	Equal variances assumed	.175	.678	-.995	58	.324	-2.516	2.527	-7.575	2.543	
	Equal variances not assumed			-.987	52.092	.328	-2.516	2.549	-7.631	2.600	

The significance value (2-tailed) of the t-test was found to be greater than 0.05 ($p=0.324$). We conclude that there is no significant difference in candidate experience in males and females

Hence, we accept Ho

3.3.2. Ho: Candidate experience does not vary with the grade levels of the position for which the hiring is being done

Table 14: One-way ANOVA for candidate exp. and grade levels of respondents

One-way ANOVA

ANOVA					
Candidate experience					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	228.761	3	76.254	.802	.498
Within Groups	5322.973	56	95.053		
Total	5551.733	59			

The significance value, $p=0.498$, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, there is no significant change in candidate experience with the change in grade levels of position for which the hiring is being done.

Hence, we accept the H_0

FINDINGS

As per the study and the statistics presented earlier, we observe that in our representative sample, 56.7% of the respondents were male and 43.3% respondents were female. 55% of the respondents belonged to the Gen Z in the age group of 18-24 years and 30% belonged to the age group of 25-40 years.

We observe that there is a moderate positive correlation between the two variables AI and candidate exp. with a Pearson's Correlation score of 0.572. This implies that if organisations increased the implementation of AI in their hiring processes, candidate experience for potential employees is likely to increase.

We conducted T-test and ANOVA tests to check if the candidate experience of the respondents varies between males and females. It is observed that there is no significant difference in candidate experience between males and females. Also, we conducted ANOVA test to check if candidate experience would vary between different grade level the respondents interviewed for. Again, there was no significant difference in candidate experience between different grade levels in which the respondents applied for.

One question that was asked to the respondents was whether human-interaction would give them better experience rather than a full-fledged AI driven process and following were the responses:

Table 15: Human Interaction desirability

CX12					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2	2	3.3	3.3	3.3
	3	2	3.3	3.3	6.7
	4	9	15.0	15.0	21.7
	5	16	26.7	26.7	48.3
	6	21	35.0	35.0	83.3
	7	10	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

The question was on a 7-point Likert scale from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree' (Strongly agree score=7 and Strongly disagree score=1). Out of 60 respondents 10% strongly agreed to this statement and 35% agreed to this statement that human interaction would give them better experience rather than a full AI driven process.

Lastly, the respondents were asked if they were more likely to recommend the company that implements AI, as an employer to their friends, families and acquaintances and following were the results.

Table 16: Employer branding scores

Employer branding					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	2	3.3	3.3	3.3
	2	5	8.3	8.3	11.7
	3	12	20.0	20.0	31.7
	4	28	46.7	46.7	78.3
	5	13	21.7	21.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Out of 60 respondents, 28 respondents gave a score of 4 on a Likert scale from 1 to 5. 1 being "Not at all likely" and 5 being "Most likely". 13 respondents are most likely to recommend an organisation if it implements AI in its hiring processes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Organisations can implement AI tools for processes such as Application tracking and resolution of queries and concerns while applying for the position.
2. Implementing chatbot systems can be beneficial to keep the candidate engaged throughout the hiring process he/she undergoes.
3. Organisations need to find the right balance between implementing AI and keeping the human touch, especially in India. As many job seekers are still under the process of understanding the AI disruption and still expect and enjoy a certain level of human touch to the entire process.
4. AI powered tools for providing personalized experiences with job recommendations based on their skillsets, search history, similar job openings can be suggested to such potential employees.
5. There could be an AI powered screening for candidates. Every candidate can be given a "candidate fit score" based on their skillsets mentioned on the CV rather than a subconscious or conscious bias of the recruiter while screening.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study is limited to 60 respondents who interviewed with IT based organisation in India. This may not give a clear understanding of how candidate experience is impacted due to AI intervention in the talent acquisition process across industries. Also, the results could vary between different industries, organisations and regions.

Hence, a similar study can be conducted for various industries and across a larger sample size that will help us gauge the readiness of our job seekers across various generations when they encounter AI processes in organisations. It will also help us understand the extent to which the AI disruption has occurred in India wherein the business environment is changing so dynamically and drastically in such a small span of time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be stated that these set of respondents are a representative sample and The results could vary for a larger sample size. However, it can be seen that introducing AI in the Talent Acquisition process will definitely have a positive impact on the candidate's experience.

AI for talent acquisition is growing to become a very crucial aspect of the HR technology ecosystem and such systems can be implemented not only to improve candidate experience but also to remove the mundane and repetitive tasks in the hiring process.

We can state that AI processes in Talent Acquisition could have a lasting impression in the minds of the candidates that could go a long way in creating an employer brand for the organisation in the market.

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